

Morphometric Study of Lower End of Fibula and Its Clinical SignificanceArumugam. K¹, Hemalatha. M², Neil James³, Kalaikumar⁴¹Associate Professor, Department of Anatomy, Tirunelveli Medical College, Tirunelveli²Senior Assistant Professor, Department of Anatomy, Tirunelveli Medical College, Tirunelveli³Senior Assistant Professor, Department of Anatomy, Tirunelveli Medical College, Tirunelveli⁴Tutor, Department of Anatomy, Tirunelveli Medical College, Tirunelveli

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Abstract:

Introduction Since human beings are obligate bipedals, the body weight is transmitted to the ground through lower limbs. The talocrural joint is one of the major weight bearing joints in our body. The Ankle joint is the most frequently injured one. Morphometric study of facet for talus is useful for reconstructive surgeries of the ankle joint. Methods 50 fibula bones (25 right & 25 left) were taken from the Department of Anatomy, Tirunelveli Medical College, Tirunelveli. Results The mean anteromedial distance of facet for talus is on right side 24.79 mm \pm 5.13, and on left side 19.13 mm \pm 2.97. The mean posteromedial distance of facet for talus is on right side 26.12mm \pm 5.78 and on left side 19.17mm \pm 2.03. The mean maximum width of facet for talus is on right side 25.88 mm \pm 5.60 and on left side 18.54mm \pm 2.36. The mean maximum height of facet for talus is on right side 27.63 mm \pm 6.28 and on left side 20.94 mm \pm 2.59. 90% of the facets for talus are triangular, 8% triangular and 2% circular in shape.

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Introduction

The fibula is one of the two bones in the leg which is otherwise called the calf bone. Fibula is the laterally placed of the two bones in the leg.

Though the fibula is not important for weight bearing, it plays an important role in the stabilization of talocrural joint, which is the chief weight bearing joint of the body. The weight of the body is transmitted through tibia and fibula, to the talus, from where it is distributed anteriorly and posteriorly within the foot. Because of the higher incidence of ankle injury due to the increase in speed of motor vehicles on the road, and the fibula playing an important role in stabilizing the talocrural joint, the morphometric study of the lower end of fibula will be helpful in the reconstructive surgeries of ankle joint, and manufacturing implants.

Materials & Methods

The study was conducted with adult human fibulae, taken from the Department of Anatomy, Tirunelveli Medical College, Tirunelveli. A total of 50

bones (25 right & 25 left sided) were selected. These bones were of undetermined age and sex, and the all the fibulae were assigned numbers. The measurements were taken using a vernier caliper (0-200 mm with a precision of 0.01 mm). The following parameters were recorded.

1. Anteromedial length of facet for Talus
2. Posteromedial length of facet for Talus
3. Maximum width of facet for Talus
4. Maximum length of facet for Talus
5. Shape of articular facet of facet for Talus.

Exclusion criteria – Damaged fibula, and fibula affected by any pathology.

Statistical methods like mean, SD, and test for equality of variances were used for analysing the data.

Results

The results obtained in this study have been tabulated in the following tables (Tables 1 & 2).

Table 1: Various distances of facet for Talus.

S. No.	Parameters	Side	Mean(mm)	Standard Deviation	P value
1	Anteromedial length	Right	24.79	5.13	0.100
		Left	19.13	2.97	
2	Posteromedial length	Right	26.12	5.78	0.000
		Left	19.17	2.03	
3	Maximum width	Right	25.88	5.60	0.000

		Left	18.54	2.36	
4	Maximum Height	Right	27.63	6.28	0.003
		Left	20.94	2.59	

The test for equality of variances returned a significant p-value of less than 0.05 for all the parameters except anteromedial length of facet for talus, which indicates a significant difference in the value of those parameters between the right and left sides.

Table 2: Shape of facets of Talus

Shape	Numbers (Out of 50)	Percentage
Triangular	45	90
Quadrangular	4	8
Circular	1	2

Figure 1: Illustration showing measurement of anteromedial distance of the facet for talus

Figure 2: Illustration showing measurement of posteromedial distance of the facet for talus

Figure 3: Illustration showing measurement of maximum width of the facet for talus

Figure 4: Illustration showing measurement of maximum height of the facet for talus

Figure 5: Circular shape of the facet for talus

Figure 6: Quadrangular shape of the facet for talus

Discussion

The morphometry of the distal end of fibula is important for manufacturing prosthesis for ankle arthroplasty reconstruction surgery.

Table 3: Comparison of anteromedial distance of the facet for talus

Name of the study	Year of the study	Mean value(mm)
[5] Naidoo N et al	2015	Male 19.18±2.27 Female 18.39±2.22
[10] Juned Labbai et al	2018	Rt : 19.71± 1.8 Lt : 19.87 ± 2.10
[11] Peter Ericson Lingamdenne et al	2019	18.62±2.45
Present study	2024	Rt 24.79 Lt 19.13

Table 4: Comparison of posteromedial distance of the facet for talus

Name of the study	Year	Mean value(mm)
[5] Naidoo N et al	2015	Male 19.18±2.27 Female 18.39±2.2
[10] Juned Labbai et al	2018	Rt 19.91± 1.81 Lt 20.44 ± 2.05
[11] Peter Ericson Lingamdenne et al	2019	19.76±2.17
Present study	2024	Rt 26.12 Lt 19.17

Table 5: Comparison of maximum height of the facet for talus

Name of the study	Year	Mean value (mm)
[3] M.S. Patiet al	2012	Radiological - 27.2 Bone – 23.7
[4] Shirishkumar et al	2014	Rt : 20.07 ± 1.9 Lt : 19.94 ± 1.81
[6] Raza HKTet al	2015	Rt : 23.7 ± 2.2 Lt : 23.7 ± 2.2
[10] Juned Labbai et al	2019	Rt : 20.6 ± 1.60 Lt : 20.6 ± 2.10
[12] Vishal Bhadkariya et al	2021	Rt 19.02 Lt 19.06
[13] Rajeev Mukhia et al	2022	Rt 17.5±0.24 Lt 16.9±0.14
Present study	2024	Rt 27.63 Lt 20.94

Table 6: Comparison of maximum width of the facet for talus

Name of the study	Year	Mean value (mm)
[5] Naidoo N et al	2015	Male : 18.77±2.27 Female : 17.14±1.5
[10] Juned Labbai et al	2018	Rt 18.03± 1.98 Lt 18.07± 2.14
[12] Vishal Bhadkariya et al	2021	Rt 17.54 Lt 16.84
[13] Rajeev Mukhia et al	2022	Rt 13.6±0.15 Lt 13.4±0.10
Present study	2024	Rt 25.88 Lt 18.54

Most of the measurements for the facet of talus are in the same range as that of other studies, but the distance is somewhat more on right side when compared to other studies which shows more on left side.

Table 7: Comparison of shapes of facet for talus

Name of the study	Year	Shapes of facet for talus (in %)			
		Triangular	Circular	Quadrilateral (Diamond)	Pear
[12] Vishal Bhadkariya et al	2021	69.56 Rt 82.60 Lt	0 Rt 4.34 Lt	4.34 Rt 0 Lt	26.08 Rt 13.04 Lt
Present study	2024	90	2	8	0

The number of fibula bones with triangular shaped facet for talus was comparable to other studies. Quadrilateral shaped facets were observed in 8% of the bones, and circular shape in 2% of the bones.

Conclusion

The morphometric study of the lower end of fibula is distinctive and gives valuable information in the advancement of management and design of prosthetics regarding the talocrural joint.

The results of this study will help in the reconstructive surgeries, and in the construction of implants for ankle joint.

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